

MADE IN NIGERIA CERAMIC KILN FURNITURE USING KAOLIN AND BALL CLAY FROM AFOWA IN ETSAKO WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, EDO STATE

Abstract

The objective of this study is to identify and harness some solid mineral deposits found in Etsako West Local Government Area in Nigeria's Edo State in order to make usable kiln furniture. The study was carried out through fieldwork, laboratory tests and studio experiments. The kiln furniture developed were support props for standing batt, prop-connectors for connecting two different props to gain height, prop-stoppers for leveling, two arranged props and platform-batts for loading ceramic ware during firing in the kiln. The produced kiln furniture was fired hard to (1250°C) in the potter's kiln. The efficiency of the kiln furniture was tested in the laboratory and the result used in making adjustments in its composition to aid the final production. The research revealed the possibility of producing durable heat resistant kiln furniture using locally available materials, furniture that can withstand stress under load over a wide range of temperatures. The crux of this article supports the use of local technology for the sustainability of the ceramic industry in the country and to a large extent reduces the dependency on imported ceramic accessories and equipment.

Keywords: Kiln furniture, kaolin, firing

INTRODUCTION

The raw materials for the production of kiln furniture are found in most parts of Nigeria, sometimes in open fields, elsewhere as minerals deeply buried within the earth. These minerals referred to as kaolin and ball clay exist as natural deposits. For a long time there has been mining of these solid minerals for several uses, but not for the production of ceramic kiln furniture. As a result, Nigeria's contemporary ceramic industry depends wholly on imported kiln furniture for its operations. This is a problem since every industrial sector in Nigeria, including ceramics, should have a degree of self-reliance in sourcing and processing its raw materials in order to facilitate the production of components that would ensure steady and continuous fabrication. Even though the local production of refractory kiln furniture remains a challenge,

it is not an insurmountable one, and this study examines the possibility of actually producing kiln furniture using raw materials from Nigeria.

Ceramists O.D. Ayodele, A.M. Ahuwan, U.A.A. Sullayman, and D.S. Yawas (2013 p. 28) define a kiln as "a ceramic oven where ceramic wares are being fired" and kiln furniture as the refractory shelves and support-posts with which ceramic wares are fired in the kiln." Thus, kiln furniture must be produced of minerals with refractory properties. Since such materials are known to occur in Edo North, Etsako West Local Government Area in Edo North Senatorial District of Edo State, Nigeria, this study focused on that area. Not only because of its numerous deposits of relevant raw materials (Fatuyi 2009 pp. 12-13), but also because of its proximity to Benin. In 2012, the researcher paid several visits to designated areas within

Edo North to locate deposits with the assistance of a resource person with a true knowledge of the neighbourhood, and harness raw materials for the production of refractory kiln furniture. See Plates 1 and 2

THE OBJECTIVES

As previously noted, kiln furniture includes such components as props, platform batts, supports and shelves for placing pottery ware inside the kiln for firing. The specific objectives were fourfold: making a contribution towards enhancing ceramic production in Nigeria by producing kiln furniture locally, determining the recipe from the chemical and physical properties of the raw materials collected and examined in the lab, experimenting with the production of refractory kiln furniture that would withstand high temperature, and producing actual kiln furniture that would withstand tear-fracture after a laboratory test. Towns visited were Auchi, Jattu, Ayogiri, Afana, Imiegba, and Ekpesi.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research method used in this study was studio-practice. This involved production of kiln furniture from selected raw materials and testing it to determine efficiency. The entire process was divided into six stages: sourcing the raw materials, processing the raw materials, seeking and servicing equipment needed for the production of the kiln furniture, drawing up recipes from the processed materials, experimenting with the processed raw materials, and firing the refractory kiln furniture. The materials used in this study included kaolin, ball clay, and sodium silicate. The equipment used for production of kiln furniture included a constructed pressing machine, metal moulds of different shapes (circular and triangular), a hydraulic jack, a

Modulus of Rupture Testing Machine (MOR), and a ceramic kiln. The study used raw materials such as kaolin and ball clay from Afowa, Afana and Imiegba in Etsako West Local Government Area, Edo state. To reach the clay deposits at some of the locations visited, shovels aided the clearing of vegetation, while diggers were used to break up the top

Plate 1

soil. Digging and clearing made it easier to get the amount of raw material required for the work. The best places to look for clay deposits were open fields around the countryside and remote villages, since the activities of land developers around the populated town of Auchi made digging on property a suspicious activity. The sourced kaolin and ball clay had to be processed to be usable. To process a small test piece, a wooden mortar was used to crush the raw material and pound it into fine grain (powder). Large batches of the raw materials were taken to the mill (see Plate 1) for pulverizing, that is, transforming it into fine powder. This was bagged and labelled for easy identification. The researcher also had to source the needed equipment and tools to produce the kiln furniture, and so fabricating a metal press and metal moulds was necessary.

Before conducting the experiments, part

productions was then generated from a simple line blend in order to determine the ratio of combined materials that would constitute a substantive composition. (See Tables 1-3 in appendix).

The compositions from the line blends were compounded and made into slabs with the following dimensions: 12 x 6 x 2 inches with an incised line of 10 cm on the flat side of the slab to calculate for bone dry strength, dry shrinkage, fire shrinkage and water of absorption. When bone dry, the slabs were measured. Composition numbers 1-3 recorded 10% shrinkage, numbers 4-8 recorded 5% shrinkage while numbers 9-11 recorded 4% shrinkage. They were then fired in the kiln to a temperature of 1300°C to determine their firing strength. Composition numbers 1-3 showed signs of vitrification with networks of cracks, numbers 4-8 were vitrified with no signs of cracks while numbers 9-11 did not show signs of vitrification as they broke easily when crushed by hand. The three line blends of kaolin from different sites (Afana, Afowa and Imiegba) but located within the same Local Council Area gave similar results. Therefore, from the three line blends, the compositional blend of the materials that exhibited some qualities of good firing strength were chosen from No.4 and No.8 respectively to form the substantive blend. This became the basis for further adjustment in the final composition from which circular props and boats were produced. Kaolin from Afowa, Imiegba and Afana gave the same result. Therefore, suffice it to say that kaolin used in this study represents Etsako kaolin.

The substantive blend was composed of 200 grams of kaolin, 200 grams of crushed hard fired kaolin consisting of three different dust-free grain sizes (6mm, 3mm, and 1mm). 50 grams of ball clay served as a binder. 50 grams of Flint were added though flint could be omitted. If absent, the ratio of the kaolin must be increased by 50 grams to bring the batch to

a total of 500 grams. All the materials were brought together in big plastic bowl and thoroughly stirred with little water to achieve a good damp blend. This was put into a metal mould, rammed, and placed under a metal press to better compact the composed blend into a compressed shape (See Appendix, Figure 1).

Plates 2-9

The above procedure was repeated using the description for circular props with assigned weight in the appropriate measure, summarized above. (See Appendix, Figure 2).

The weighed materials were placed in an open plastic bowl to make for an easy mixture of the constituent materials. A small amount of water was required to dampen the mixture in order to avoid warping during and after the forming stages. After thoroughly mixing the various ingredients, they were put into a cylindrical metal mould and rammed into place. After this, it was taken to the press to compress it into a hard mass aided by a hydraulic jack, then extruded from the mould to achieve a dry press within a production time of 5 minutes. The diverse types of props, including the different sizes of hollowed cylindrical props, cylindrical connectors, and cylindrical stoppers were made successfully using this method. See Plates 2 to 8.

All the items produced from the test experiments were fired in the potter's kiln to a temperature of 1,250°C. This was carried out under a strict firing procedure that lasted for almost twenty-five hours (exceeding one day). The props, batts, connectors and stoppers were stacked in line with accepted loading procedures in ceramics, allowing proper circulation of heat within the kiln. (See Plate 9). The firing was conducted in a liquid fuel down draft kiln. The firing procedure involved preheating to allow for the gradual expulsion of the water of plasticity within the temperature range of 100°C to 150°C. This was maintained for about six hours to gradually allow for expulsion of steam in order to prevent breakage of the loaded furniture within the kiln during the early stages of firing. After this point, the pre-

Plates 10-13

heating continued with a gradual rise in temperature to 240°C. Gradual heating continued for another three hours to bring the temperature to 730°C. When there was no visible sign of steam coming through the spy-hole of the kiln, and after maintaining a steady temperature of 750°C for an extra hour, the actual blast commenced at exactly 12 hours after loading. The spy-holes remained opened until the fifteenth hour to arrive at 900°C. Then all vents were closed to increase the kiln temperature. That the interior of the kiln was red hot with a clear atmosphere and the cones standing upright was observable through the spy hole. A rise in temperature of the kiln from 900°C to 1,150°C was achieved by the twentieth

hour. Heat blasts continued for an additional extra four hours to arrive at 1260°C. At this temperature, 'cone 12' placed inside the kiln bent over. This was an indication that the maturing temperature had been reached. At that moment, it was time to shut down the burners to end the firing operation. When the kiln had cooled down it was opened in order to unload the fired kiln furniture.

The different components of the fired kiln furniture were labelled and sent to the Laboratory, where Modulus of Rupture (MOR) tests were carried out. These included impact, compression and bend tests. The efficiency and functionality of the kiln furniture produced were confirmed (Plates 10-13).

FINDINGS

- * Laboratory tests revealed that local raw materials have chemical and physical properties as desirable as foreign raw materials for kiln furniture.
- * A locally constructed press can serve as effectively as a foreign made one for compressing the composed raw materials used in production of kiln furniture.
- * Kiln operators should observe prolonged pre-heating at a low temperature of 80°C to 200°C for a period of at least 1.05 hours when firing kiln furniture in the potters' kiln for the very first time before engagement to full blast. This is to prevent shattering.
- * Locally produced kiln furniture tested in the laboratory proved to resist tear-fracture as in the case of foreign ones.
- * Kiln furniture that can withstand temperatures as high as foreign furniture can be locally produced.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study grows out of a drive for national development, since there is an economic benefit to being self-reliant and able to ensure steady and continuous production. The article presents outcomes that are now available to ceramists and potters. The kiln furniture produced was presented as one of the several requirements for equipment and tools at the Ceramic Unit, Delta State University, Abraka, for their 2015 accreditation exercise. The relevance of the results is further buttressed because the utilization of local minerals offers new avenues for entrepreneurship and job creation through producing the materials necessary for manufacturing ceramics in Nigeria. The kiln furniture developed through this research also facilitates rapid progress in the firing of ceramic ware in the potter's kiln. Perhaps most important is that the refractory kiln furniture produced from the locally sourced raw materials was tested and found to be a suitable substitute for imported kiln furniture.

The researcher also has the following recommendations to make as a result of the processes he followed as a practicing ceramist. Raw materials identified as kaolin and ball clay collected from Afowa, Afana, Imiegba and Ikpeshi towns are suitable for the production of refractory kiln furniture for industrial purposes. When firing kiln furniture for the very first time, operators should observe prolonged pre-heating at low temperature of 80°C to 200°C for a period of at least 1.05 hours before engagement to full blast to prevent furniture from shattering. To keep the flat batt from warping under the weight of the load placed on it during the firing operation, the flat side should be alternated during each firing exercise. Flat batts should not be placed on a bare floor when not in use. They are better placed leaning against the wall. Also, to prevent damage to kiln furniture when being transported, soft pads should be

placed between batts and crates provided for props. Moreover, packages for transporting kiln furniture should always be labelled as 'fragile.' Should kiln furniture break, do not discard it. It can be recycled into grog for producing new kiln furniture.

Kiln furniture has been produced successfully using local raw materials found within Etsako West Local Government Area, Edo State in Nigeria, making the local production of kiln furniture in Nigeria a real possibility. This study complements and adds to previous research efforts on the local production of kiln furniture. The findings of this research have been systematically documented in text and pictorial form. Local substitutes for foreign industrial component parts such as props, platform batts, supports and shelves should greatly speed up ceramic production because the resources expended on imported kiln furniture could be ploughed into other areas of need within Nigeria's ceramic industry.

CAPTIONS

Plate 1: Corn Mill used for milling raw materials. Photo: Eweka 2012.

Plate 2: Filled mixture in cylindrical mould. Photo: Eweka 2012.

Plate 3: Kennedy Eweka ramming clay mixture into the cylindrical mould. Photo: Studio Assistant 2012.

Plate 4: Kennedy Eweka filling a rectangular mould. Photo: Studio Assistant 2012.

Plate 5: Kennedy Eweka released circular prop. Photo: Studio Assistant 2012.

Plate 6: Kennedy Eweka demonstrates ramming by hand. Photo: Studio Assistant 2012.

Plate 7: Metal Press used for compacting the mould. Photo: Eweka 2012.

Plate 8: Released compressed batt freed from press machine. Photo: Eweka 2012.

Plate 9: Produced kiln furniture loaded in the kiln in preparation for firing. Photo: Studio Assistant 2012.

Plate 10: Fired props labelled for laboratory test. Photo: Eweka 2012.

Plate 11: Fired connectors and stoppers labelled for laboratory test. Photo: Eweka 2012.

Plate 12: Rockwell Impact Testing Machine located at the Mechanical Engineering Laboratory, University of Benin, Benin City, used for the test. Photo: Eweka 2013.

Plate 13: Engineer G. I. Onaghise conducting MOR test (Modulus of Rupture Test) on the produced kiln furniture, using the Universal Testing Machine at the Mechanical Engineering Laboratory, University of Benin, Benin City. Photo: Eweka 2013.

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SUBSTANTIVE COMPOSITION FOR FLAT BATTS FROM THE STUDY

Material	Percentage	Grams
Etsako Kaolin	40%	200 grams
Kaolin Grog (Coarse grains)	40%	200 grams
Ball Clay	10%	50 grams
Flint	10%	50 grams
Total	100%	500 grams

SUBSTANTIVE COMPOSITION FOR CIRCULAR PROPS FROM THE STUDY

Material	Percentage	Grams
Hard Grog (Dust free)	40%	200 grams
Etsako Kaolin	40%	200 grams
Ball clay	10%	50 grams
Flint	10%	50 grams
Total	100%	500 grams

Tables 1-3

Table 1: Simple Compositional Line Blend Ratio of Material – Afowa Kaolin

S/	Raw	No	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	No
N	Materi	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
	al		2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
1	Kaolin	10	90	80	70	60	50	40	30	20	10	0
		0										
2	Hard	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	10
	grog											0

Table 2: Simple Compositional Line Blend Ratio of Material for Afana Kaolin

S/	Raw	No	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	No
N	Materi	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
	al		2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
1	Afana	10	90	80	70	60	50	40	30	20	10	0
	kaolin	0										
2	Hard	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	10
	grog											0

Table 3: Simple Compositional Line Blend Ratio of Material for Imiegba Kaolin

S/	Raw	No	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	No
N	Materi	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
	al		2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
1	Imiegb	10	90	80	70	60	50	40	30	20	10	0
	a kaolin	0										
2	Hard	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	10
	grog											0

Figures 1 and 2

